

AI-BASED TOOLS for research

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Name	webpage	Description
		Multi task research platform
Avidnote	avidnote.com/	Avidnote is a tool for researchers. Easily write and organize your research. Use AI to write, read and analyze data
IRIS and IRIS workspace	Iria.ai	Literature search and analysis. Iris workspace also can summarize articles and abstracts Chat with your data
		Research support
B!son	service.tib.eu/bison/	B!SON helps you to find a suitable Open Access journal for your publication
scisummary	scisummary.com	Summarize a pdf
Tavily	www.Tavily.com	The report you get out is a precise answer to the question.
Consensus	consensus.app/	Ask a research question and the app will search articles. This is not a generative KI.
chatpdf	Chatpdf.com	Chat with your pdf

Pdf	Pdf.ai	Chat with your pdf
Inciteful	Inciteful.xyz	You enter one or more articles and get a graphic representation of what is common
unisilo	discovery.researcher.life/publisher	"Determined to make it easier for researchers and innovators to find analogous concepts and novel ideas from different industries and fields."
Yewno	Yewno.com	Semantic map and navigation-based topics. Connected to medicine databases and databases of clinical trials
Keenious	Keenious.com	Comes with suggestions for articles that can be referenced while writing a text
ConnectedPapers	ConnectedPapers.com	Navigation between articles
SemanticScholar	SemanticScholar.org	Creates a list of articles
Research rabbit	Research rabbit.ai	Navigation based on authors and topics
Open knowledge maps	openknowledgemaps.org /	Creates groups and clusters of articles based on topics
Annif	Annif .ai	Automatic indexing and classification of documents
Feedly	Feedly.com	A research assistant monitors the web for relevant information related to a research topic
Readwise reader	readwise.io/read	Ghostreader is your GPT-3 copilot of reading. Ask questions. Define terms. Simplify complex language. Have also text to speech.

Rayyan	Rayyan.ai	Simplifies the work with systematic overviews
As-review	www.asreview.nl	Simplifies the work with systematic overviews. Open source and run locally on the computer.
Humata	Humata.ai	Ask questions across all of your files
notebookLM	notebooklm.google	Collaborate with a virtual research assistant! Create also a podcast from an ar When you upload the documents that are central to your projects, NotebookLM instantly becomes an expert in the information that matters most to you.
Tana	tana.inc/knowledge-graph	Tana is a knowledge graph. Just like how a map shows how different cities and towns are connected by roads, a knowledge graph shows how different concepts and entities are connected to each other. This way of connecting information aligns more closely with how the human brain works compared to traditional databases, giving you a set of capabilities in Tana that are impossible to achieve with other tools. «“Tana is one of the few knowledge management tools that moves beyond mimicking static text on paper. It takes the computational medium seriously. It gives regular folks access to a set of powerful primitives that previously only developers could touch.”
Covidence	www.covidence.org	Simplifies the work with systematic overviews
DistillerSR	www.distillersr.com	“From a systematic literature review to a rapid review to a living review, DistillerSR makes any project simpler to manage and configure to produce transparent, audit-ready, and compliant results.”
Eppi review	eppi.ioe.ac.uk	Simplifies the work with systematic overviews
Elicit	Elicit.org	Elicit can find relevant papers without perfect keyword match, summarize takeaways from the paper specific to your question, and extract key information from the papers

Paper digest	www.paper-digest.com	Summarize articles
Litmaps	Litmaps.com	From a single paper, Litmaps generates a map of the most relevant articles that relate to your seed paper
Scholarcy	Scholarcy.com	Summarizes articles
Ripeta	Ripeta.com	Summarizes articles & check the research quality of your article
GitHub Copilot	github.com/features/copilot	Uses the OpenAI Codex to suggest code and entire functions in real-time, right from your editor
Scite	Scite.ai	Ask a question to scite, and get an answer backed by real research. Scite finds also sources for claims made by language models, and finally it finds if research has been supported or contrasted
Proofig	Proofig.com	Check the integrity of the images from your research
Open AI Whisper	openai.com/research/whisper	openAI based speech to text
MacWhispers		speech to text based on OpenAi. Native to macOS
Upword	Upword.ai	summarize text
you	you.com	The AI Search Engine You Control
Metaphor systems API	metaphor.systems	Metaphor is a search engine designed from scratch using AI

Carrot2	search.carrot2.org/#/search/web	“Carrot2 organizes your search results into topics. With an instant overview of what's available, you will quickly find what you're looking for.”
Andisearch	www.andisearch.com	Andi, your smart search assistant
		Writing support
Writefull	Writefull.com	Change the language to a more academic style
Paperpal Preflight	paperpal.com/preflight	Check your paper before submitting to a journal
Trinka	Trinka.ai	AI-rewrite support in addition to the grammar check
Grammarly GO	Grammarly.com	AI-rewrite support in addition to the grammar check
Scribendi	Scribendi.com	Scribendi has an AI-based software one can download.
Jenni	Jenni.ai	Search for references while writing. It check also for plagiarism
		Digital Humanities
Transkribus	readcoop.eu/transkribus/	Text recognition, image analysis, and structural recognition of historical documents
Loghi		Same as transkribus, but installed locally on your computer.
eScriptorium	eScriptorium (.uk)	Digital Paleography

		Text generators
OpenAI ChatGTP		An AI-powered Chabot
Bard		A creative and helpful collaborator from GOOGLE, to supercharge your imagination, and boost your productivity!
Copilot		Microsoft text and document generator
Perplexity	Perplexity.ai	An AI-powered chatbot. Like chatgpt, but gives concise answers to a question, with some references
Scipub+	scipubplus.com/	Academic writing assistant
Jasper	Jasper.ai	Create texts for blogs
Longshot	Longshot.ai	The AI writer ensures unique, fresh, fact-checked, SEO-friendly content
Frase	Frase .io	Use keywords or sentences to create text
SlidesAI	SlidesAI.io	Google-based service that produces slides based on text
Quillbot	Quillbot.com	Rewrite your text
Copyshark	Copyshark.ai	create text
Resoomer	Resoomer.com	Create a resume of large sections of text
Textio	Textio.com	Check a text for social bias
Copy	Copy.ai	An AI writer
Writesonic	Writesonic.com	This tool write plagiarism free, blog article, SEO content, and emails

LMstudio	lmstudio.ai/	Platform to test various LLM on a laptop
Claude	www.anthropic.com/news/claude-3-family	Claude language model
		Other AI-based tools
Hamlet	hamlet.andromedayelton.com/	Checks all master's theses at MIT that may be relevant to a given thesis
Vespa	Vespa.ai	Structured text and vector search
Azure	azure.microsoft.com	Microsoft platform that analyzes all types of documents performs text recognition and image recognition and structures them
Scinote	Scinote.net	Lab help, but you can also write an introduction for a paper based on some keywords
Ghostwriter	replit.com	Ghostwriter uses AI to help you write better code, faster
NoCode	Nocode.ai	Build AI Solutions without Coding
Bit	bit.ai	Workplace platform, supported by AI
There's an AI for that	Theresanaiforthat.com	A list of AI tools for various human activities
Listening	Listening.io	Listen a journal article read for you

Global campus	globalcampus.ai/	Find literature, experts or journals across the globe.
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NB: AI-based software for image generation and processing etc. are not include

